

The teaching of Sociology in dispute: Education as a political act of resistance in the sociological perspective of Erlando da Silva Rêses

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Abstract

The interview conducted on February 26, 2026, with Brazilian Black popular educator and sociologist Erlando da Silva Rêses constitutes a valuable testimony regarding the formative and intellectual trajectories that permeate his personal and professional path. Between memories and reflections, Professor Rêses revisits significant fragments of his life history, outlining how Sociology became embedded in his academic and existential journey, establishing itself as a structuring axis of his teaching practice and his critical reading of the social world. Throughout the conversation, the interviewee reflects on the role of the sociologist in the 21st century, exploring the dilemmas and tensions that shape the training of Sociology teachers in Brazil, as well as the political and ideological disputes surrounding the presence and intermittence of the discipline within school curricula. In a narrative that is simultaneously analytical and memorialistic, Rêses highlights the role of Sociology in fostering citizenship and emancipation, emphasizing the processes of consolidation and institutionalization of the field, particularly with the creation of the Professional Master's Degree in Sociology in the National Network (ProfSocio). Finally, he outlines a sensitive and critical overview of the paths, challenges, and perspectives of Sociology teaching in Brazil, reaffirming the discipline as a space of resistance, imagination, and political commitment to social transformation.

Keywords: Teaching of Sociology; Teacher Education; Educational Policies; ProfSocio.

Erlando da Silva Rêses is a professor at the Faculty of Education (FE) and at the Graduate Program in Education at the University of Brasília (PPGE/UnB). His academic and sociological production encompasses diverse themes ranging from public education policies and popular education to teacher training and Youth and Adult Education. Through studies and reflections on the Teaching of Sociology, his work has resonated within the academic community across different regions of Brazil, particularly in the training of specialized Sociology teachers for secondary education, contributing to the advancement of Brazilian sociological production in the field of teaching. He holds a Ph.D. in Sociology from the University of Brasília (UnB, 2008), with the dissertation *From Vocation to Profession: Teacher Union Organization and the Social Identity of Teachers*. He also earned his Master's, Bachelor's, and Licentiate degrees in Social Sciences from the same institution (UnB, 2004, 1998). He completed a postdoctoral fellowship in Education at the University of London (2019–2020), focusing on Social Theory, Historical-Dialectical Materialism, and Labor Pedagogy. He serves on the editorial boards of national academic journals in the fields of Education and Sociology. Currently, he is a Full Professor at the Faculty of Education (FE/UnB)¹, leader of the Research Group on Historical-Dialectical Materialism and Education (CONSCIÊNCIA), and coordinator of three extension projects: 1) Integrated and Emancipatory Training for Access to Higher Education (FORMANCIPA); 2) LeiA – Reading and Playful-Pedagogical Action for Children; 3) Training of Literacy Educators and Educators of Young, Adult, and Elderly Workers. He is also a member of the Research Group on Labor (GEPT) at the Institute of Social Sciences (ICS), Department of Sociology at UnB. He coordinated the Specialization Course in Teaching of Sociology through CAPES/MEC (2008–2011) and the Education and Diversity program at UnB, with an emphasis on Youth and Adult Education (2013–2014 and 2014–2015). He is a co-founder of the International

¹ The interview took place on February 26, 2026, shortly after the defense of the descriptive-analytical memorial for promotion to Full Professor at the Faculty of Education (FE/UnB), by Erlando da Silva Rêses, entitled “Progressive Popular Education, Historical-Dialectical Materialism, and the Indissociability between Teaching, Research, and Extension.”

Network of Researchers on Associativism and Trade Unionism of Education Workers (ASTE Network). For his extension projects, he was awarded the 2nd Paulo Freire Education Prize by the Legislative Chamber of the Federal District (CLDF, 2024) and twice received the Annual Human Rights Education Award – Mireya Suárez, granted by the University of Brasília (UnB, 2024 and 2025). Among his extensive sociological production, the following works stand out, authored, co-authored, or organized by him: *Artificial Intelligence, Labor, and Capitalism* (2025); *Value and Labor Exploitation: Platform Capitalism and COVID-19* (2023); *Labor, Youth and Adult Education, and Emancipatory Technologies* (2021); *Socialist Pedagogy, Labor, and Education* (2021); *Gypsy Identity and School Education: Traditional Knowledge and Ethnic Conflict* (2018); *Youth and Adult Workers' Education: Policies and Experiences of Integration into Professional Education* (2017); *Sociology in Secondary Education: Citizenship and Social Representations of Teachers and Students* (2016); *From Vocation to Profession: Teacher Unionism in Basic Education in Brazil* (2015); and *University and Social Movements* (2015).

Fagno da Silva Soares and Rafael Bezerra Gaspar (FSS and RBG): Good evening, esteemed Professor Erlando Rêses. We express our sincere appreciation for your willingness and promptness in kindly accepting to participate in this interview. To begin our dialogue, we would like to invite you to revisit your life history and your trajectory in the field of education. What inspirations led you to choose a career as a sociologist and a Sociology teacher? How did your educational background unfold, and what paths marked the journey that brought you to teaching and research?

Erlando da Silva Rêses: Good evening, dear Fagno and Rafael. I thank you for the invitation to this interview; it is a pleasure to be, once again, alongside my

friend Mário Bispo² in a production focused on the teaching of Sociology. I am from Ceará, a Black man, descendant of the Indigenous peoples of Caucaia (CE), and father of Dandara Barroso Rêses, who gives meaning and continuity to my journey. A Popular Educator by conviction and a university professor by profession, I have built my trajectory between the school ground and spaces of critical formation. I worked as a Sociology teacher in Basic Education within the Secretariat of Education of the Federal District (SEEDF) for thirteen years, cultivating sociological thinking as a tool for emancipation. Before that, I dedicated ten years to literacy for youth and adults and to the training of educators in Youth and Adult Education (EJA), in dialogue with popular and social movements, reaffirming my commitment to a transformative education rooted in the realities and resistances of the Brazilian people. Well then, if memory serves me correctly, this must be the eighth time I have had the opportunity to address the role of entities such as the Brazilian Sociological Society (SBS), the National Association of Graduate Studies and Research in Social Sciences (ANPOCS), and the National Federation of Sociologists (FNS) in the process that led to the approval of Law No. 11,684/2008, which made Sociology mandatory in secondary education. As I have previously mentioned, there was strong mobilization from different organizations in defense of the approval of this law. Prior to that, it is important to recall that there was intense activity within the National Congress, the Ministry of Education (MEC), and the National Council of Education (CNE). I remember that, together with the Philosophy professor Erasmo Baltazar Valadão, we organized a petition and personally delivered it to Congressman Padre Roque (PT-RS), the author of the amendment to the LDB that established the mandatory inclusion of Sociology and Philosophy in secondary education. I would particularly highlight the role of the National Federation of Sociologists (FNS) and, more

² Mário Bispo dos Santos is a sociologist and a reference in the field of Sociology teaching in Brazil, distinguished by his significant contribution to teacher education and to the consolidation of the discipline in basic education. His academic and intellectual trajectory is marked by a commitment to articulating sociological theory and pedagogical practice, advocating for a critical, contextualized, and socially relevant Sociology teaching.

specifically, certain unions such as the Sociologists' Union of the State of São Paulo (SINDSESP). Here in the Federal District, we also participated through a pre-association of sociologists or, more precisely, through the reestablishment of such an association. Colleagues from the South, especially from Rio Grande do Sul, were also involved, although more through the field of Philosophy, yet there was a relevant mobilization taking place. Regarding ANPOCS, to the best of my knowledge, its participation was quite limited. It may have merely signed a collective document circulated to gather institutional support, but as a scientific entity, it did not engage in direct political action, whether in Parliament, within the MEC, or alongside the government. Therefore, it was an intense movement of individuals and institutions, and there are records of this process. A significant portion of this documentation was produced by our colleague Lejeune Mirhan Xavier de Carvalho from São Paulo, in more than one publication, which include photographs capturing several moments of the political engagement of these organizations and individuals.

***FSS & RBG:** Professor Erlando, could you tell us about the theoretical influences that shaped your academic trajectory, from your undergraduate studies to your doctoral training at the University of Brasília (UnB), as well as your entry into teaching? Which sociologists or other intellectuals played a decisive role in your initial education and in the development of your thinking throughout your career?*

Erlando da Silva Rêses: It is evident that the responses tend to complement each other, since I have, to some extent, already begun to address this point when discussing my entry into teaching. However, the question is broader, as it also concerns theoretical influences from undergraduate studies through the master's and doctoral levels.

Throughout my academic trajectory in the Social Sciences, I soon perceived a strong affinity with Marxist theory. Naturally, the sociological field is vast, both in theoretical and methodological terms, but my engagement has always been closely linked to social and popular movements. I recall that, at that time, we participated

in formative meetings that generally took place on Saturdays and Sundays. These were moments of collective study, during which we read texts and discussed works by various authors.

It was in this context that I had more intense contact with the works of Paulo Freire, such as *Education as the Practice of Freedom*, *Cultural Action for Freedom*, *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*, and *Pedagogy of Autonomy*, among others. These readings brought us closer to a critical perspective committed to emancipation and social transformation. This engagement emerged from an extension project of the Faculty of Education (FE) focused on literacy for youth and adults, in which I actively participated. I had forgotten to mention this in my first response. The project was coordinated by Professor Maria Luiza Pinho Pereira. It was a highly significant experience, allowing me to articulate educational practice with theoretical reflection, profoundly influencing my later trajectory as both a teacher and researcher.

This engagement was indeed very intense there was a clear sense of affinity with certain readings and debates that were articulated both within the university and in social movements. In the formative meetings held within these movements, we used to discuss texts and authors from different theoretical traditions, although the Marxist orientation was always strongly present. We read classical texts by Karl Marx, which facilitated our identification with the field of Social Sciences, but we also engaged with other perspectives in order to establish contrasts and foster critical debate.

I particularly recall a course I attended with great dedication, which was part of the curriculum and titled “Marxist Sociological Theory.” I truly committed myself: I spent nights reading the assigned texts in order to attend classes fully prepared. At times, I studied throughout the night and left home around six in the morning. During that period, I lived in the southern outskirts of the Federal District and it would take me about two hours or more, depending on traffic, to reach the University of Brasília (UnB), where classes were held. I would leave home having only a cup of coffee, trying to stay awake, and head straight to the university. It was a phase marked by great effort, but also by intense intellectual enthusiasm and commitment to my education.

Other texts were also part of my formation, both in Sociology and in Anthropology and Political Science. At that time, there was the possibility of pursuing a degree in Anthropology, but I chose a different path: I completed a bachelor's degree in Sociology along with a teaching degree in Social Sciences. These two qualifications profoundly shaped my trajectory. During my undergraduate studies, I came into contact with many classical authors as well as contemporary thinkers, all of whom contributed to the construction of my worldview and my teaching practice.

When I began working as a teacher in the Secretariat of Education of the Federal District (SEEDF), I sought to make effective use of this theoretical repertoire, always striving to connect content with social reality and with the life experiences of students. This approach was deeply rooted in our Marxist framework, which places at the center of the educational process the understanding of concrete reality and historical conditions of existence. Our focus was precisely to articulate theory and practice, knowledge and lived experience, in order to contribute to processes of social transformation.

Professor Mário Bispo, in fact, has developed an interesting line of research on this topic, in which he identifies different teaching profiles. He distinguishes, for example, between the so-called “specialist teacher” one who comes from academia and tends to reproduce theoretical knowledge and the “advanced user,” who critically appropriates such knowledge, adapting it to pedagogical practice and to students' realities.

There was also another type of teacher and I partly identified with this profile who, although familiar with the field, did not possess specific training in Sociology. This teacher relied on various materials and strategies to bring sociological content closer to students, seeking to make the discipline more accessible and meaningful. In a way, this approach made Sociology more experiential, more connected to students' everyday lives. I myself felt somewhat positioned between these two profiles. Although, if I am not mistaken, I was classified within Professor Mário Bispo's research group as a “specialist,” I perceived myself as a teacher who moved between perspectives combining Marxist, Bourdieusian, and other theoretical frameworks, always with the aim of bringing sociological knowledge closer to students' daily lives.

At the master's and doctoral levels, this trajectory took on new contours. During my undergraduate studies, driven by this same theoretical formation and intellectual inquietude, I conducted research on participatory political culture and administrative decentralization, using as a case study the Participatory Budget implemented in 1995 in the Federal District, during the so-called Democratic Popular Government. In this work, we analyzed processes of social participation and discussed how individuals defined their priorities in order to transform, even partially, the structure of local public policies.

This study was closely connected to debates on the welfare state, which at that time was being impacted by neoliberalism. It was the period of the governments of Fernando Collor de Mello and later Fernando Henrique Cardoso, during which neoliberalism became consolidated and deepened in Brazil. It was within this context that we developed a critical reflection on the limits and possibilities of popular participation and democratic governance.

At the master's level, my focus shifted to the teaching of Sociology, in research developed in close collaboration with Professor Mário Bispo, who had been investigating, since 2002, the profiles and practices of Sociology teachers. The field research involved the selection of groups of students for analysis through focus groups, and once again, Marxist theory served as our central framework, while also engaging with contributions from Social Psychology, which helped us understand the subjective and formative dimensions of teaching.

Within Social Psychology, our main references included authors such as Serge Moscovici, Willem Doise, Denise Jodelet, and others associated with the theory of social representations. At that moment, our interest was to understand how students perceived Sociology as a subject in secondary education, what meaning it held in their lives, their formation, and their everyday experiences. The research involved two groups of students: one from schools located in central areas of the city and another from peripheral areas. This comparison allowed us to observe significant differences in how Sociology was understood and valued by distinct social groups.

In general, this was my academic trajectory: during undergraduate studies, there was a strong presence of Political Sociology and Sociology of Education, although with greater emphasis on the former. At the master's level, the focus shifted toward Sociology of Education, with occasional connections to Sociology of Work. Finally, at the doctoral level, I concentrated more systematically on Sociology of Work, while maintaining dialogue with Sociology of Education.

In my doctoral dissertation, my main interest was to investigate how teachers in Brazil were formed and organized through trade unions, using the state of Rio de Janeiro as a case study, a major urban center and former federal capital. From this context, I sought to understand how teachers structured themselves politically and developed collective forms of struggle, articulating their union practices with the construction of a professional and social identity within the teaching profession.

My dissertation, entitled *From Vocation to Profession: Teacher Union Organization and the Social Identity of Teachers*, defended at the University of Brasília (UnB) in 2008, represents an effort to understand the constitution of the professional and political identity of basic education teachers in Brazil, based on their forms of collective organization and the historical processes of mobilization that have shaped the teaching profession in recent decades.

The work later resulted in the book *From Vocation to Profession: Teacher Unionism in Basic Education in Brazil*, in which I further developed the analyses presented in the dissertation. In this work, I more consistently engaged with the field of Sociology of Work, seeking to understand the teacher as an intellectual worker and political actor, whose struggles and organizations reflect both the contradictions and the potentials of Brazilian public education.

The starting point of this research was the tension between vocation and professionalization in teaching. On the one hand, vocation appears as the symbolic, moral, and affective dimension of the profession, historically associated with the idea of “calling” and personal dedication. On the other hand, professionalization expresses the legitimate pursuit by teachers of social recognition, material valuation, and technical autonomy.

Based on this duality, I sought to understand how teachers recognize themselves and are socially recognized, especially within a context marked by the precarization of teaching labor, the expansion of neoliberal policies, and the structural transformations of Brazilian public education. I selected the state of Rio de Janeiro as the empirical field, due to its historical role as a political center and as a space of intense union struggles and teacher movements.

My objective was to understand the dynamics of organization, resistance, and the construction of collective identity among teachers within their representative organizations. Thus, I analyzed both the historical trajectory of teacher unionism its phases of emergence, consolidation, and reconfiguration and the discourses and practices that articulate “being a teacher” with “being a worker.”

From a theoretical standpoint, I engaged with authors from the Sociology of Work and the Sociology of Professions, such as Pierre Bourdieu, Claude Dubar, Luc Boltanski, Alain Touraine, and António Nóvoa, in addition to incorporating reflections from Political Sociology and Social History of Labor. This framework allowed me to discuss the social construction of teaching, emphasizing processes of recognition, legitimacy, and collective belonging that shape contemporary teacher identity.

Methodologically, I combined documentary research, interviews with union leaders, and discourse analysis, seeking to articulate empirical data with a consistent theoretical reflection on the role of professional organizations as mediating spaces between the individual and the collective, between everyday school life and broader structural struggles for the valorization of teaching.

The results revealed that teaching in Brazilian basic education is undergoing a process of transition: from an idealized and altruistic vocation toward a profession marked by tensions between precarization and political affirmation. In this trajectory, teacher unionism plays a decisive role by contributing to the reconfiguration of teachers’ self-image as intellectual workers, producers of knowledge, and political agents of social transformation. At the same time, the research revealed the contradictions of this process internal disputes, institutional limitations, and tensions between emancipatory ideals and the pressures of market-

oriented educational policies. In summary, with *From Vocation to Profession*, I sought to develop a critical reflection on the political and identity dimensions of teaching, understanding the teacher not merely as a mediator of knowledge, but as a historical, collective, and political subject embedded within contemporary social struggles. I believe that this study contributes both to the fields of Sociology of Education and Sociology of Work, as well as to the public debate on the recognition and valorization of the teaching profession, reaffirming the centrality of teachers in the construction of a democratic educational project.

***FSS & RBG:** Throughout your career, we observe a strong interest in themes related to teaching and teacher education, especially in the field of Sociology. Could you tell us about your interest in these topics in your research investments and how you have contributed to the training of young teachers? Furthermore, in your view, what limitations are still present within public policies for advancing programs aimed at strengthening the teaching profession, whether in the academic sphere, in the workplace itself, or in initiatives that encourage young people to enter teacher education programs?*

Erlando da Silva Rêses: The development of my interests in the field of teaching and teacher education, particularly within Sociology, is deeply connected to my concrete experience in public policy and curriculum development processes, as well as my engagement in university extension activities. Since the beginning of my academic and professional trajectory, I have sought to understand both the limits and possibilities imposed by educational policies on the consolidation of Sociology teaching, as well as to identify programs and actions capable of strengthening the teaching profession.

This interest emerged largely from my own experience as both a student teacher and a practicing educator, when I was able to perceive, in practice, the challenges of the profession and the distance that often exists between theoretical formulations and the everyday reality of schools. Thus, teacher education became not only an object of research but also a field of intervention and political-pedagogical commitment.

After completing my undergraduate studies and before beginning my master's degree, I experienced a period of intense involvement in curriculum development, actively participating in the formulation and reformulation of the Sociology curriculum within the Secretariat of Education of the Federal District (SEEDF). It was an extremely rich and challenging moment, marked by extensive research, meetings, and debates with teachers from the public school system, in which we collectively sought to understand what should be taught in Sociology and how to translate the theoretical foundations of the discipline into pedagogical terms.

There was a constant concern among us to bridge theory and teaching practice we wanted teachers to concretely understand the intentions behind the proposed curriculum. At the same time, we sought to build the process collaboratively, carefully listening to colleagues' contributions and systematizing ideas into a coherent and democratic proposal.

From this experience emerged the First Sociology and Philosophy Meeting of the SEEDF, where we gathered and presented meaningful pedagogical experiences aligned with the curricular guidelines under development, giving visibility to the strength of the work carried out in schools. This event was particularly significant for me, as it represented an important step in consolidating Sociology as a formative field and in strengthening teacher education in the area. It was a moment of collective learning and intellectual maturation, in which I more firmly understood that teacher education is also constructed through dialogue, exchange, and collective reflection on pedagogical practice.

I also recall with appreciation the experience promoted by Professor Sadi Dal Rosso, retired from the Department of Sociology at UnB, who created through extension activities a course entitled "*Updating in Sociology*," aimed at the continuing education of teachers from the SEEDF. The goal was to foster dialogue between the university and basic education by inviting faculty members from the Department of Sociology to teach classes and share their research with public school teachers.

I had the opportunity to participate in one of the editions of this initiative, alongside Professor Mário Bispo and other colleagues from the Secretariat of

Education. It was an extremely enriching experience that reaffirmed the importance of maintaining ongoing connections between academia and basic education. This experience further strengthened my commitment to teacher education and to the consolidation of Sociology in secondary education.

Our engagement with the field of Philosophy also intensified during this period, especially through Professor Ana Miriam, author of the book *Thinking Philosophy*, who developed a remarkable continuing education initiative. Inspired by similar concerns, she organized the program “*Thinking the Teaching of Philosophy*,” primarily directed at teachers in the public education system.

Through this collaboration, one of the later versions of that program evolved into “*Thinking the Teaching of Philosophy and Sociology*,” in which we dedicated particular attention to the integration between the two fields. This shared experience between Sociology and Philosophy was fundamental in consolidating an interdisciplinary perspective on teaching and reaffirming the formative role of the humanities within public education.

From that point forward, my work also expanded into the field of teaching materials. I was part of the team that developed the first National Textbook Program (PNLD) for Sociology, a historic milestone for the discipline. Years later, I participated again in a more recent edition of the program. These experiences were decisive because, in thinking about textbooks, we were also, in a sense, thinking about teacher education since pedagogical materials are among the main mediators between academic knowledge and classroom practice.

Subsequently, I consolidated my engagement with teacher education within the Faculty of Education, where I have worked as a professor since 2009. Since then, this has been one of my primary areas of academic interest: understanding and strengthening the formative processes of teaching, both in their theoretical and practical dimensions.

Currently, I coordinate four extension programs and projects, among which I highlight FORMANCIPA – Integrated and Emancipatory Training for Access to Higher Education. This project was designed to articulate teaching, research, and

extension around teacher education and the democratization of access to higher education. Within FORMANCIPA, undergraduate students from different fields go to secondary schools to teach in an integrated and interdisciplinary manner, facing the challenge of overcoming the disciplinary fragmentation that still characterizes much of Brazilian education.

This trajectory reinforces a conviction that has guided me from the beginning: training teachers is a political, ethical, and emancipatory act, and the teaching of Sociology, alongside other fields in the humanities, occupies a fundamental place in this process of critical and civic education.

The major challenge faced, together with students involved in these projects, is precisely to move against the fragmentation of teaching: to design and implement integrated classes in which two or three fields interact in the education of secondary school students, especially those preparing to enter higher education through the ENEM or traditional entrance examinations.

This proposal seeks not only to strengthen the knowledge required for continuing studies but also to reaffirm the formative and emancipatory meaning of education. Our commitment to this field remains strong because we understand that training teachers and strengthening the profession means investing in the future of public education itself.

However, it is necessary to acknowledge that public policies aimed at teacher education have been weakened, particularly in recent years, marked by budget cuts, discontinuity of programs, and the devaluation of the humanities. The Human Sciences, in particular, have suffered significant impacts, whether through reduced investment or through selective policies that silence and marginalize critical thought.

What we observe is an attempt to impose a kind of “intellectual gag,” aimed at silencing teachers and researchers committed to critical reflection and civic education. This is a troubling context, marked by political and ideological persecution, which directly threatens the autonomy of the educational field and the role of public schools as spaces of freedom, thought, and social transformation.

Nevertheless, I remain convinced that resisting and working in teacher education is a concrete way to confront these adversities. It is in everyday practices in the classroom, in extension projects, in teacher education programs, and in educational networks that we reaffirm our commitment to a critical, democratic, and socially engaged education.

***FSS & RBG:** How do you evaluate the trajectory and development of Sociology teaching in Brazil in recent years? From this perspective, how do you perceive the current situation of the discipline in the country, and what characteristics would you highlight in the profile of secondary school Sociology teachers, especially in light of your experiences in the Federal District?*

Erlando da Silva Rêses: Historically, there has been a lack of respect for the duality present in academic training between research and teaching. This division, still deeply rooted in universities, reflects an old legacy within the Brazilian educational structure and resembles the duality found in secondary education, reinforced by Provisional Measure No. 746/2016, which reformed this level of education.

This logic, which separates education aimed at continuing studies from that oriented toward the labor market, reproduces class divisions and deepens inequalities. Within the university context, this split manifests in the opposition between researcher and teacher, often reinforced by academics themselves, who tend to prioritize research over teacher education.

Our reflection, however, seeks precisely to overcome this fragmentation by proposing an integration between pedagogical practice and investigative thinking. As a teacher and teacher educator, I believe that teaching should lead to research, and that research, in turn, should find meaning in teaching practice. The teaching of Sociology, in this sense, has sought to subvert this dichotomous logic, demonstrating that it is both possible and necessary to articulate theory and practice, teaching and critical reflection, in a complementary rather than oppositional relationship.

However, this effort encounters deep cultural and structural resistance. The teaching profession in Brazil continues to suffer from a lack of social and material recognition. Teachers are often symbolically celebrated acknowledged in speeches and tributes but rarely valued in concrete terms. There is rhetorical respect for teachers without corresponding investment in working conditions, adequate salaries, or professional valorization policies.

This contradiction is intensified by a context of increasing precarization: low wages, insufficient infrastructure, overcrowded classrooms, and excessive workloads. Moreover, daily interaction with youth in schools, marked by social tensions and challenges, has placed increasing demands on teachers, often without adequate institutional support. These factors have contributed to the low attractiveness of the profession, discouragement regarding career continuity, and a sense of disillusionment among many educators.

Another concerning issue is the rise of school violence and related phenomena such as bullying and burnout syndrome, which, although often treated as individual problems, actually reflect the structural precarization of teaching labor and the intensification of emotional and cognitive demands placed on teachers.

All these elements symbolic devaluation, material precarization, and psychological pressures have combined to weaken the teaching profession, particularly in the humanities, which have in recent years faced explicit ideological persecution and systematic budget cuts.

Although these issues are not entirely related to the academic duality, this duality is fundamentally cultural. We are heirs to a scientific tradition strongly tied to research conceived under the principle of distance the so-called epistemological vigilance. This tradition holds that the researcher must remain as distant as possible from their object of study, as if scientific objectivity depended on the denial of the subject who investigates.

This conception, although historically legitimized, reflects an epistemological perspective strongly influenced by the hard sciences, positivism, and other currents that engage little with materialist and dialectical approaches. As a result, the

prevailing model of science is hegemonized by a rationality reproduced within academia, shaping not only the understanding of teacher education but also the conception of classroom practice itself.

This perspective ultimately limits the transformative potential of education and restricts scientific practice to a technical and depoliticized horizon, when, in fact, knowledge should function as an instrument of emancipation and commitment to social reality.

***FSS & RBG:** It is quite common to observe, in undergraduate programs, a greater emphasis on the training of researchers to the detriment of teacher education an asymmetry that reflects a hierarchical and dualistic view between scientific practice and teaching practice. In your assessment, do Social Sciences programs still reproduce this inequality? What paths or alternatives do you envision to transform this scenario and promote a more integrated articulation between research training and teacher education already at the undergraduate level?*

Erlando da Silva Rêses: Indeed, undergraduate programs in Social Sciences still display a strong asymmetry between the training of researchers and the training of teachers. This inequality stems from a historically consolidated conception of science that privileges distance, neutrality, and objectivity as markers of scientific legitimacy, to the detriment of the pedagogical, ethical, and political dimensions that constitute the educational act.

This is a positivist and hierarchical legacy that fragments the field of Social Sciences and reproduces, within universities, a dichotomy between scientific practice and teaching practice. It is therefore essential to overcome this dualistic logic through an integrated and dialogical formation, in which teaching and research are understood as complementary dimensions of the same process of knowledge production and socialization.

Thus, teaching Sociology is not merely about transmitting content, but about forming critical subjects capable of understanding and intervening in social reality.

This implies recognizing that teaching practice is also a form of research a space for reflection and theoretical reconstruction grounded in concrete experience.

The paths to transforming this scenario involve epistemological and pedagogical reform within Social Sciences programs. It is necessary to strengthen disciplines and formative experiences that articulate theory and practice, research and teaching, recognizing the school as a space of knowledge production rather than merely a site of application.

In this sense, I emphasize the importance of reflective supervised internships, action research, and praxis-based training, in which future teachers can understand teaching as a political, ethical, and emancipatory act. By promoting the integration between research training and teacher education, the goal is not only to correct an institutional imbalance but to affirm a broader conception of science one committed to social transformation and to the humanization of educational practices, grounded in a critical and emancipatory sociological pedagogy.

***FSS & RBG:** The first doctoral dissertation to take the teaching of Sociology as its object of study dates back to 2002. Since then, it has been observed that graduate programs in Sociology, with few exceptions, still demonstrate limited interest in the theme of teaching, maintaining relatively weak research lines in this area. As a result, the knowledge produced in these spaces tends to take time to reach basic education, remaining largely confined to academia. In your assessment, what is the current place occupied by the teaching of Sociology in Brazilian graduate studies? And, based on your experience, what paths could favor the incorporation of this production into programs and policies aimed at strengthening Sociology in basic education?*

Erlando da Silva Rêses: The place of Sociology teaching within Brazilian graduate education remains, to a large extent, peripheral and subordinate. There is a historical dissociation between the field of sociological research and the field of teaching, which results in the formation and reflection on teaching being frequently relegated to a secondary level.

This epistemological hierarchy, rooted in a positivist and academicist tradition, assigns greater prestige to theoretical production detached from educational practice, reinforcing the idea that teaching is merely a space for the application of knowledge rather than one of creation and reconstruction. This separation is not only institutional, but also epistemological and political. It reveals a conception of science that denies the formative and emancipatory dimension of knowledge, reducing teaching to a technical practice.

For this reason, I advocate for the recognition of Sociology teaching as an autonomous and critical field of research, capable of producing knowledge about its own practice and establishing an organic dialogue between university and school.

In this sense, the place of Sociology teaching in graduate education should be that of a space of convergence between theory and practice, in which teaching is recognized as an act of intellectual and political production. It is therefore necessary for graduate programs to incorporate research lines and groups dedicated to teacher education, curriculum, and teaching methodologies, recognizing the school as a legitimate locus of sociological investigation.

This implies adopting an epistemological perspective that breaks with the paradigm of scientific neutrality and recognizes teaching as a constitutive dimension of Sociology itself. Such a space must be formative, capable of integrating teaching practice and research as inseparable moments of sociological and political formation, understanding the teaching of Sociology as a practice of resistance and citizenship formation, committed to the critical reading of social reality.

Thus, incorporating academic production from graduate studies into programs aimed at strengthening Sociology in basic education requires building bridges between university and school, transforming research into an instrument of collective reflection, continuing education, and intellectual emancipation. The challenge is not merely to bring sociological knowledge to the school, but to produce it with the school, within a dialogical, democratic, and transformative perspective.

FSS & RBG: *In this context, do you consider that the Professional Master's Degree in Sociology in the National Network (ProfSocio)³ can constitute an effective path to bringing knowledge produced in graduate education closer to classroom reality, through the work of teacher-researchers? What strategies would be necessary to strengthen and expand ProfSocio in the coming years so that it is incorporated and valued by an increasing number of graduate programs in Sociology?*

Erlando da Silva Rêses: The Professional Master's Degree in Sociology in the National Network (ProfSocio) undoubtedly represents a promising path for ensuring that knowledge produced in graduate education effectively reaches the classroom through the work of teacher-researchers. In my experience, this proposal has proven to be quite fruitful, especially because it encourages articulation between higher education and basic education.

I recall, in fact, a previous experience within CAPES aimed at training Basic Education teachers, particularly those who did not yet have specific training in Sociology. Between 2009 and 2010, a specialization course was created with the objective of strengthening this connection between university and school, bringing academic production closer to everyday pedagogical practices.

³ The Professional Master's Degree in Sociology in the National Network (ProfSocio) emerged from a collaboration between public universities, CAPES, and the Brazilian Sociological Society (SBS), aiming to strengthen the continuing education of Basic Education teachers. Initial discussions took place in 2015, highlighting the need for teacher qualification following the mandatory inclusion of Sociology in secondary education in 2008. In 2016, the project was developed and submitted to CAPES, being approved in 2017 under the PROEB program. In the same year, the national coordination was established at the Federal University of Ceará (UFC). Academic activities began in 2018, with cohorts distributed across different regions of the country. Since then, the program has been consolidated as a space for knowledge production on the teaching of Sociology, promoting the articulation between theory and practice. The expansion of the network with new institutions has strengthened its scope and impact. In 2020, ProfSocio was more effectively integrated into the UAB system, adopting hybrid teaching during the pandemic. Between 2021 and 2023, the program underwent academic consolidation, curricular revision, and strengthening of interinstitutional research. Its CAPES rating of 4 attests to its quality. Currently, it brings together more than 15 institutions and stands out in the training of teacher-researchers, contributing to the valorization of Sociology and the humanities in basic education.

In my view, ProfSocio continues and expands this movement by strengthening the dialogue between sociological theory and teaching practice, recognizing the school as a legitimate space for knowledge production and sociological inquiry. To ensure its strengthening in the coming years, it is essential to guarantee consistent funding, consolidate interinstitutional research and training networks, and promote the recognition of professional master's programs within Sociology graduate studies. Only in this way will it be possible to consolidate an academic culture that values teaching as an essential dimension of sociological practice and civic education.

The organization of the Specialization Course in Teaching of Sociology, developed by CAPES/MEC in partnership with the Center for Open and Distance Education (NEaD) at the Federal University of Mato Grosso (UFMT), within the framework of the Open University of Brazil (UAB) in 2009–2010, represented an important initiative aimed at training Basic Education teachers in Sociology. I had the opportunity to participate in its development as a content author and member of the coordination team.

The course materials served as a reference for subsequent initial and continuing teacher education experiences in the field of Sociology teaching. The curriculum was structured into two theoretical-practical modules:

- Module 1: Memory and Formation; Memory and Teaching Practice; Teaching Sociology: Contents and Methodologies
- Module 2: History of Sociology; Culture and Identity; Social Structure and Social Change; Political Participation and Citizenship; Methodology and Teaching Resources

These modules sought to articulate theoretical and practical foundations, valuing teaching experience and the collective construction of knowledge. It was a highly meaningful experience, as it brought together Basic Education and higher education teachers, fostering reflection on practice and strengthening the link between university and school.

In this context, ProfSocio emerges as a continuation and expansion of this trajectory, transforming academic knowledge into educational practice and new forms of interpreting social reality.

***FSS & RBG:** Law No. 11,684, enacted on June 2, 2008, made Philosophy and Sociology mandatory subjects in all years of secondary education, reaffirming a commitment to the formation of critical, reflective citizens capable of understanding and intervening in social reality. Considering this context, what paths could favor the definitive consolidation of Sociology in the basic education curriculum?*

Erlando da Silva Rêses: Despite the historically limited interest of some graduate programs in Sociology teaching, this field has a significant tradition. Over time, this reality has changed, and the field has strengthened considerably since the beginning of the 21st century.

Currently, graduate education produces increasingly consistent academic work, supported by research groups, laboratories, academic events, and professional associations that contribute to consolidating the field. However, this progress remains vulnerable to public policy fluctuations, especially in relation to funding for research and scholarships.

The approval of Law No. 11,684 represented a major milestone, ensuring the presence of Sociology and Philosophy as mandatory subjects. However, its implementation still faces challenges, such as teacher training, curricular integration, and institutional resistance.

***FSS & RBG:** Finally, in your opinion, what are the main dilemmas and challenges faced by sociologists and Sociology teachers in the 21st century?*

Erlando da Silva Rêses: We are living in a moment in which the teaching profession, especially in Sociology, faces not only pedagogical challenges, but also political and existential dilemmas. Among the main challenges are the discontinuity

of public policies, the weakening of investments in teacher education, and the fragility of mechanisms that connect universities and schools.

Additionally, there has been a decline in incentives for young people to enter teacher education programs, particularly in the Humanities, which compromises the generational renewal of the profession.

I argue that advancing and strengthening the teaching profession necessarily depends on the consolidation of permanent policies for initial and continuing teacher education, capable of integrating theory and practice and recognizing teachers as intellectuals and political agents.

Despite the adversities, it is precisely within this context that the urgency of reaffirming the critical and emancipatory role of education becomes evident.

***FSS & RBG (Closing):** Professor Erlando Rêses, we express our deep gratitude for this thorough interview and for the eloquence of your reflections, which allowed us to journey through the complex paths of Sociology teaching in Brazil. Between gestures of hope and flashes of sociological imagination, we continue to learn that teaching is also an act of resistance, and that each class can be a political, poetic, and profoundly human act. Thank you for sharing with us the essence of your work and the vibrant depth of your thought.*

REFERENCES

- Rêses, E. da S., Dal Rosso, S., Gontijo, L. V., Borges, R. E. S., Lima, F. S., & Costa, S. N. (Orgs.). (2025). *Inteligência artificial, trabalho e capitalismo*. Pontes Editores.
- Rêses, E. da S., Dal Rosso, S., Valente, J. C. L., Borges, R. E. S., & Teberga, A. (Orgs.). (2023). *Valor e exploração do trabalho: Capitalismo de plataforma e Covid-19*. Pontes Editores.
- Rêses, E. da S., Pereira, M. L. P., & Cunha, M. C. (Orgs.). (2021). *Trabalho, educação de jovens e adultos e tecnologias emancipatórias* (Vol. 1). Hildebrando Editor & Autores Associados.
- Rêses, E. da S. (2021). *Pedagogia socialista, trabalho e educação* (Vol. 1). Editora da Universidade de Brasília.

Rêses, E. da S., Oliveira, C. E., & Pacífico, J. M. (Orgs.). (2020). *Educação pública em debate no Centro-Oeste e Norte brasileiros: Entre a unidade e diversidade no contexto escolar brasileiro* (Vol. 1). Sustentável; Edufro.

Rêses, E. da S., & Perpétuo, L. D. (2018). *Ciganidade e educação escolar: Saber tradicional e conflito étnico* (Vol. 1). Tagore Editora.

Rêses, E. da S., Silveira, D. A., & Pereira, M. L. P. (2017). *Educação de jovens e adultos trabalhadores: Análise crítica do Programa Brasil Alfabetizado* (Vol. 1). Paralelo 15.

Rêses, E. da S., Sales, M. C., & Pereira, M. L. P. (Orgs.). (2017). *Educação de jovens e adultos trabalhadores: Políticas e experiências da integração à educação profissional* (Vol. 1). Mercado de Letras.

Rêses, E. da S., Santos, M. B. dos, & Rodrigues, S. D. (2016). *A sociologia no ensino médio: Cidadania e representações sociais de professores e estudantes* (Vol. 1). Fino Traço.

Rêses, E. da S. (2015a). *De vocação para profissão: Sindicalismo docente da educação básica no Brasil* (Vol. 1). Paralelo 15.

Rêses, E. da S. (2015b). *Universidade e movimentos sociais* (Vol. 1). Fino Traço.

Santos, M. B. (2014). O PIBID na área de Ciências Sociais: Condições epistemológicas e perspectivas sociológicas. *Revista Brasileira de Sociologia*, 2(3).

Santos, M. B. (2002). *A sociologia no ensino médio: O que pensam os professores da rede pública* (Dissertação de mestrado). Universidade de Brasília.

Soares, F. (2018). Por uma história do ensino de sociologia no Brasil: Na oficina sociológica de Cristiano Bodart tomando café com sociologia. *Revista Observatório*, 4(6), 1007–1029.